

Supplemental Appendix for Restoring Trust in US Elections through Effective Election Administrator Messaging

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Contents

A Illustrative Examples of Focus Group Messages with Images	1
B Survey Question Wording	2
C Order of Questions	6
D Statistical Power	7
E Sample Descriptive Statistics Before and After Listwise Deletion	8
F Focus Group Protocol	10

A Illustrative Examples of Focus Group Messages with Images

Partisan Power Appeal

Clever/Humorous Appeals

@PateforIowa

#VoterID is the law in Iowa. Every voter will be asked to show ID at the polls on Tuesday. Jedi mind tricks won't help you. Make sure you're #VoterReady.
voterready.iowa.gov

B Survey Question Wording

For all questions, missing responses are listwise deleted.

Political interest: Do you consider your interest in politics to be very great, great, some, little, or are you not interested in politics at all?

1. Very great
2. Great
3. Some
4. Little
5. Not at all
6. Unsure/Prefer not to respond

Party identification: Generally speaking, do you usually think of yourself as a Democrat, a Republican, an Independent, or what? Then ... Would you call yourself a strong [Democrat/Republican] or a not very strong [Democrat/Republican]? ... OR Do you think of yourself as closer to the Republican Party or to the Democratic Party?

1. Strong Democrat
2. Not very strong Democrat
3. Lean Democrat
4. Independent
5. Lean Republican
6. Not very strong Republican
7. Strong Republican
8. Unsure/Prefer not to respond

Ideology: We hear a lot of talk these days about liberals and conservatives. Here is a seven-point scale on which the political views that people might hold are arranged from extremely liberal to extremely conservative. Where would you place yourself on this scale, or haven't you thought much about this?

1. Extremely liberal
2. Liberal
3. Slightly liberal
4. Moderate, middle of the road
5. Slightly conservative
6. Conservative
7. Extremely conservative
8. Unsure/Prefer not to respond

Income: Last year, what was your total family income from all sources, before taxes?

1. Less than \$10,000
2. \$10,000 to \$19,999
3. \$20,000 to \$29,999
4. \$30,000 to \$39,999
5. \$40,000 to \$49,999
6. \$50,000 to \$59,999
7. \$60,000 to \$69,999
8. \$70,000 to \$79,999
9. \$80,000 to \$89,999
10. \$90,000 to \$99,999
11. \$100,000 - \$149,000
12. More than \$150,000
13. Unsure/Prefer not to respond

Voted in 2020: In talking to people about elections, we often find that a lot of people were not able to vote because they weren't registered, they were sick, or they just didn't have time. How about you - did you vote in the Presidential election held on November 3, 2020? (Recoded to 1 = Yes, 0 = No)

1. Yes
2. No
3. Unsure/Prefer not to respond

Education: What is the highest level of schooling you have completed?

1. Less than high school degree
2. High school degree or equivalent (e.g., GED)
3. Some college but no degree
4. Associate degree
5. Bachelor's degree or equivalent
6. Graduate or professional degree
7. Unsure/Prefer not to respond

Age: Please enter the year you were born.

Political knowledge: did the respondent correctly answer either of the two following questions? First: For how many years is a United States Senator elected: that is, how many years are there in one full term of office for a U.S. Senator?

1. 1
2. 2

3. 3
4. 4
5. 5
6. 6
7. 7
8. 8
9. 9
10. 10 or more
11. Unsure/Prefer not to respond

Second: On which of the following does the U.S. federal government currently spend the least?

1. Foreign aid
2. Medicare
3. National defense
4. Social security
5. Unsure/Prefer not to respond

Race: Which of the following best describes your racial identity (select all that apply)? (Recoded to white, Black, and other)

1. White
2. Black or African American
3. American Indian or Alaska Native
4. Asian
5. Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander
6. Some other race (please specify):
7. Unsure/Prefer not to respond

Gender: Which of the following best describes your gender identity? (Recoded to 1 = Female, 0 = Male)

1. Male
2. Female
3. Some other gender (please specify):
4. Unsure/Prefer not to respond

Conspiratorial thinking: the sum of the following questions. First: Much of our lives are being controlled by plots hatched in secret places.

1. Strongly agree
2. Somewhat agree

3. Neither agree nor disagree
4. Somewhat disagree
5. Strongly disagree
6. Unsure/Prefer not to respond

Second: Even though we live in a democracy, a few people will always run things anyway.

1. Strongly agree
2. Somewhat agree
3. Neither agree nor disagree
4. Somewhat disagree
5. Strongly disagree
6. Unsure/Prefer not to respond

Third: The people who really 'run' the country are not known to the voters.

1. Strongly agree
2. Somewhat agree
3. Neither agree nor disagree
4. Somewhat disagree
5. Strongly disagree
6. Unsure/Prefer not to respond

Fourth: Big events like wars, economic recessions, and the outcomes of elections are controlled by small groups of people who are working in secret against the rest of us.

1. Strongly agree
2. Somewhat agree
3. Neither agree nor disagree
4. Somewhat disagree
5. Strongly disagree
6. Unsure/Prefer not to respond

C Order of Questions

1. Pre-treatment trust in LEO questions
2. Treatment
3. Manipulation check
4. Unrelated survey material (20 questions)
5. Conspiracy inventory
6. Post-treatment trust in LEO questions
7. Political knowledge questions
8. Demographics (in order: age, race, gender, education, party identification, ideology, voting, political interest, income)

D Statistical Power

Table SM. 1: N in Each Condition

Condition	Other	Black	White
Control	High trust $n = 21$	High trust $n = 24$	High trust $n = 323$
	Low trust $n = 4$	Low trust $n = 7$	Low trust $n = 91$
Messenger Black Male; Message Civic Duty	High trust $n = 18$	High trust $n = 23$	High trust $n = 367$
	Low trust $n = 8$	Low trust $n = 8$	Low trust $n = 87$
Messenger Black Male; Message Experience	High trust $n = 20$	High trust $n = 24$	High trust $n = 372$
	Low trust $n = 9$	Low trust $n = 8$	Low trust $n = 87$
Messenger Black Male; Message Neighbor	High trust $n = 16$	High trust $n = 29$	High trust $n = 340$
	Low trust $n = 6$	Low trust $n = 3$	Low trust $n = 75$
Messenger Black Male; Message Rules	High trust $n = 21$	High trust $n = 18$	High trust $n = 335$
	Low trust $n = 7$	Low trust $n = 5$	Low trust $n = 66$
Messenger White Female; Message Civic Duty	High trust $n = 22$	High trust $n = 29$	High trust $n = 337$
	Low trust $n = 4$	Low trust $n = 9$	Low trust $n = 93$
Messenger White Female; Message Experience	High trust $n = 23$	High trust $n = 21$	High trust $n = 345$
	Low trust $n = 9$	Low trust $n = 3$	Low trust $n = 77$
Messenger White Female; Message Neighbor	High trust $n = 26$	High trust $n = 24$	High trust $n = 319$
	Low trust $n = 9$	Low trust $n = 6$	Low trust $n = 97$
Messenger White Female; Message Rules	High trust $n = 25$	High trust $n = 27$	High trust $n = 348$
	Low trust $n = 3$	Low trust $n = 6$	Low trust $n = 86$

E Sample Descriptive Statistics Before and After List-wise Deletion

Table SM. 2: Mean, Standard Deviation, and n of Each Variable Before and After Listwise Deletion

	Before listwise deletion			After listwise deletion		
	Mean	SD	n	Mean	SD	n
Pretreatment						
LEOs are ethical	3.405	1.275	5421	3.484	1.260	4370
LEOs follow rules	3.489	1.276	5476	3.572	1.253	4370
LEOs are free and fair	3.536	1.277	5470	3.622	1.252	4370
Low trust in elections	0.218	0.413	5361	0.200	0.400	4370
Posttreatment						
Manipulation check (name of messenger)	1.000	0.000	5561	1.000	0.000	4370
Conspiratorial thinking (plots in secret places)	2.732	1.391	5419	2.703	1.402	4370
Conspiratorial thinking (a few people run things)	3.601	1.171	5484	3.579	1.195	4370
Conspiratorial thinking (unknown people run things)	3.208	1.362	5429	3.192	1.380	4370
Conspiratorial thinking (big events controlled)	2.794	1.386	5400	2.757	1.398	4370
Sum: conspiratorial thinking scale	12.310	4.548	5242	12.231	4.593	4370
LEOs are ethical	3.371	1.189	5428	3.433	1.184	4370
LEOs follow rules	3.523	1.194	5457	3.595	1.176	4370
LEOs are free and fair	3.555	1.189	5409	3.631	1.173	4370
Change in LEOs are ethical (Post - Pre)	-0.040	0.887	5340	-0.051	0.883	4370
Change in LEOs follow rules (Post - Pre)	0.030	0.956	5405	0.024	0.943	4370
Change in LEOs are free and fair (Post - Pre)	0.015	0.891	5353	0.009	0.874	4370
Respondent knowledge (Budget)	0.202	0.402	5542	0.220	0.414	4370
Respondent knowledge (Senator)	0.496	0.500	5561	0.532	0.499	4370
Respondent political knowledge (answered either question correctly)	0.558	0.497	5549	0.594	0.491	4370
Respondent age	54.842	16.950	5454	55.403	16.807	4370
Respondent is white	0.885	0.319	5561	0.900	0.301	4370
Respondent is Black	0.072	0.258	5561	0.066	0.248	4370
Respondent is other race	0.068	0.251	5561	0.057	0.233	4370
Respondent is female	0.571	0.495	5529	0.543	0.498	4370
Respondent education	4.054	1.473	5541	4.147	1.450	4370
Respondent party identification (higher = Republican)	3.995	2.277	5336	3.968	2.294	4370
Respondent ideology (higher = more conservative)	4.230	1.737	5387	4.227	1.746	4370
Respondent voted (self-report)	0.861	0.346	5415	0.886	0.318	4370
Respondent political interest	3.429	1.143	5516	3.534	1.085	4370
Respondent income	6.802	3.426	5333	6.960	3.381	4370
Attention check (select "5G")	0.994	0.080	5561	0.996	0.062	4370

F Focus Group Protocol

-0:30 - 0:00. Zoom Session Opens

“Thank you for joining us. We will start the session in 30 minutes. During this time, we will check your tech and review your participation consent forms.

First, please make sure your camera is on.” [GO AROUND TO EACH PARTICIPANT TO MAKE SURE THEIR CAMERA WORKS]

“Now we want to make sure that we know who is speaking. Please put the name you want to be called on the screen. For those of you who do not know how to do this, hover your cursor over your picture and click on the 3 dots on the top right-hand side of your picture. When you do this, you will see an option to change your name. Remember, we only want you to use the name that you want to be called. This does not need to be your actual name. We also ask that you try to keep your camera on throughout the session unless if possible.” [GO AROUND TO EACH PARTICIPANT TO MAKE SURE THEIR PREFERRED NAMES ARE UP]

“Now we would like to make sure that everyone knows how to use the raise hand function and the chat function.” [EXPLAIN AND THEN GO AROUND AND MAKE SURE EVERYONE CAN DO THIS]

“When you signed up for the focus group, you read and signed a research consent form. To summarize, this included that you do not have to participate and can drop out at any point, that your chosen name and words may be used in research presentations, as may descriptions of your reactions, but your image or recordings of you will NOT be released to anyone outside of the research team. This session will be recorded, but again, your image or recordings of you will NOT be used for anything other than researcher review. Before we begin, do you have any questions about this?” [ANSWER QUESTIONS]

“We are going to start the recording and session now. Please remember that you may drop out at any point.”

0:00 - 0:05. Welcome and ground rules

“Thank you all again for joining us. My name is [INSERT NAME] and I am part of the trust project research team at Auburn University. We are going to spend an hour and a half today talking about how elections are run. Before we get going, I want to go over some ground rules about how this focus group is going to be run.

First, some of the things we are going to talk about people have very strong feelings and opinions about. And sometimes reasonable people disagree. We ask that you share as openly as you feel comfortable today but do your best to be polite.

Second, I will be posing questions at various times throughout the session. I may go around and call on folks for some of the questions that we want responses from everyone about—I will use the name on your screen and go in order as I see people. For some other questions, I will ask for responses more generally. If you have something to say, we ask that you raise your hand (actual or virtual) and I will call on you to share.

Finally, we want to hear from everyone and have you respond to each other as well. But we also ask that you refrain from talking over each other, or alternatively, giving long, protracted responses. If that starts to happen, I'll send a request to wrap it up through the chat function.”

0:05 - 0:10. Brief round of introductions

“We would like everyone to make some brief introductions—please share your name and the state, and if you remember, tell us what the first election you voted in was.

I will start. My name is [INSERT NAME] and the first election I voted in was [GIVE YEAR OR DESCRIBE ELECTION]. So now it's your turn.” [GO AROUND AND CALL ON EACH PERSON BY THE NAME ON THE SCREEN]

0:10 - 0:25. Baseline check: trust in elections and why

“Wonderful—thanks. The first question I have for you is about how much you trust the electoral process today. Take a minute to think about it, and then I am going to go around and I'd like you to share how much you trust elections today and why. I will go around and call on each of you.” [GO AROUND AND CALL ON EACH PERSON BY THE NAME ON THE SCREEN]. [POSSIBLE PROMPTS IF THIS GOES QUICKLY]. “There is an upcoming election—how do you feel? Which specific parts of the election are concerning to you? Why? [POSSIBLE PROMPTS TO DRAW OUT MORE INFORMATION] Why do you feel that way? Has this changed over time? Was there a time when your trust in elections was higher? When did things change? Why?”

0:25 - 0:35. Message #1: Neutral/fact-based message about election information and process.

“Now I'm going to share my screen and show you some messages about elections. We would like you to tell us what your immediate reaction is. [PROMPT A: Did you know: one in five people eligible to vote has a disability? (ACLU) Nothing should prevent you from casting your ballot! You and your Vote matters! #RegisterToVote #GoVote] [POSSIBLE FOLLOW-UP QUESTIONS] What does this message make you think about? Why did you respond that way? What about that message evoked that response?”

[PROMPT B: Attention all military or overseas Yolo County registered voters - your Vote-by-Mail ballots have been sent out! If you have friends or family living overseas and they do not receive their ballot, please have them contact us at elections@yolocounty.org or (530) 666-8133.#yourvote] [POSSIBLE FOLLOW-UP QUESTIONS] “What does this message make

you think about? Why did you respond that way? What about that message evoked that response?”

[PROMPT C: video of how ballots are processed] [POSSIBLE FOLLOW-UP QUESTIONS] “What does this message make you think about? Why did you respond that way? What about that message evoked that response?”

0:35 - 0:45. Message #2: Neutral/ election officials are your neighbors. “Now I’m going to share my screen and show you some other messages about elections. We would like you to tell us what your immediate reaction is. [PROMPT D: Tweet from Tom Hicks (EAC)—election officials are your neighbors—<https://twitter.com/RedBlue2024/status/1322978539243769860>] [POSSIBLE FOLLOW-UP QUESTIONS] “What does this message make you think about? Why did you respond that way? What about that message evoked that response?”

0:45 - 0:55. Message #3: Positive messages designed to evoke an emotional response (patriotism/ American values). “Now I’m going to share my screen and show you some other messages about elections. We would like you to tell us what your immediate reaction is.” [PROMPT D: social media post—it is your patriotic duty to vote/ the strength of American democracy depends on you voting] [POSSIBLE FOLLOW-UP QUESTIONS] “What does this message make you think about? Why did you respond that way? What about that message evoked that response?”

0:55 - 1:10. Message #4: Appeal to GOTV and being involved to get your side into power to enact legislative reform. “Now I’m going to share my screen and show you some other messages about elections. We would like you to tell us what your immediate reaction is.” [PROMPT F: Social media post—the only way to change who is in power is to vote] [POSSIBLE FOLLOW-UP QUESTIONS] “What does this message make you think about? Why did you respond that way? What about that message evoked that response?”

Message #5: Appeal to Humor. “Here are some other messages about elections. We would like you to tell us what your immediate reaction is.” Prompt G- Humorous appeal #1. Prompt H- Humorous appeal #2. [POSSIBLE FOLLOW-UP QUESTIONS] “What does this message make you think about? Why did you respond that way? What about that message evoked that response?”

1:10 - 1:15. Trust in elections- general. “For those of you who mentioned at the start of our conversation that you do not trust election results, is there anything that would make you change your mind? What needs to happen for your trust in the electoral process to change?” [CALL ON SPECIFIC PEOPLE] [POSSIBLE FOLLOW-UP QUESTIONS] “Is there someone you can think of—either you know personally or know of—who, if they said they trusted the electoral process, it would make you feel more positive?”

1:15. Closing. “Thank you all very, very much for taking the time to join us in the focus group today. The results of the focus group will be analyzed and used to support a national

survey about elections, and will also be used as we talk with election officials about what they can do better to reach out to the citizens in their communities.

If you have any follow-up questions, you can reach me by email at [INSERT PROJECT EMAIL INTO CHAT]. Finally, we have offered each participant \$75 for participation. You will receive this once all aspects of the focus group are completed. If you have questions about this, you can talk with Stephanie Bickerstaff at [INSERT PROJECT EMAIL INTO CHAT].

Thank you all again for your time!”